

Congress, Akali Conflict on Punjabi Suba Question Reflected in the Press

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Abstract The Akali Dal ran as an independent in the January 1946 elections for the Punjab Legislative Assembly, frequently running against the Congress. The Muslim League took home the most seats (73), followed by the Unionists with 11, the Akalis with 21, and the Congress with 51 (including 10 Sikh seats). The Akalis emerged as important Sikh spokespersons on partition and Pakistan-related matters. A coalition administration led by Khizr Hayat Khan was formed in March 1946 when no compromise was made with Congress or the Akalis, despite the fact that a government needed support to be formed.[1]

Keywords Akali Dal, Punjab Legislative Assembly, Congress.

Introduction

Akali Dal was represented in the Punjab Ministry by Baldev Singh, who served as Development Minister. The Sikh delegation joined the Unionist Party in opposing Pakistan. When the Shiromani Akali Dal met in the Assembly Chamber in Lahore on March 21, 1946, Master Tara Singh stated that he supported a united India but that he would support a separate Sikh State with the option to federate with either India or Pakistan if Pakistan's demand was met.[2]

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to study the Congress, Akali conflict on Punjabi Suba question reflected in the press.

Review of Literature

In March 1946, the Shiromani Akali Dal formally endorsed the goal of a Sikh State. "Whereas the Sikhs, who are closely linked to Punjab through sacred shrines, property, language, customs, and history, claim it as their homeland and sacred land, which the British took as a trust from the last Sikh ruler when he was a minor, and whereas the Sikhs entity," the resolution stated. It is being threatened on account of the persistent demand for Pakistan by the Muslims on the one hand and of the danger of absorption by the Hindus on the other, and Executive Committee of the Shiromani Akali Dal demands for the preservation and protection of the religious cultural and economic and political rights of the Sikh population and their important sacred shrines and historical Gurdwaras with provision for the transfer and exchange of population and property".[3]

In a statement, Master Tara Singh had declared on 4 April 1946 that, "We want a Sikh State in a united India.... such a state will belong to the Sikh Panth, but it will be democratic and not monarchical".[4] Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru had himself made a statement on April 4, 1946 that "redistribution of provincial boundaries was essential and inevitable. I stand for semi- autonomous units as well...I should like them (the Sikhs) to have a semi-autonomous unit within the province so that they may experience the glow of the freedom".[5]

On 5th April 1946, Sardar Patel declared: "Sikhistan issue will be considered in the Constituent Assembly after the transfer of power in the hands of the Indians".[6] On 6th April 1946, Master Tara Singh declared: "The Sikh will not tolerate the inclusion of Punjab in Pakistan. We shall be contented with a Sikh State in free India".[7]

In July 1946, Jawaharlal Nehru himself told a press conference at Calcutta: The brave Sikhs of Punjab are entitled to special considerations. I see nothing wrong in an area and

a set up on the North wherein the Sikhs can also experience the glow of freedom.[8] Giani Kartar Singh, the Secretary of Akali Party had stated: "The Sikhs should be allowed to form an independent State of their own in North India".[9] The Congress Party emerged as the strongest political force and assumed political power in the Punjab after partition. Dr. Gopi Chand Bhargava was elected Chief Minister and Sir Chandu Lai Trivedi was appointed Governor.[10] Gopi Chand Bhargava formed the new ministry on 11 June 1948 which included Swaran Singh and Isher Singh Majhail and Udham Singh Nagoke. Mohan Singh Nagoke, who was the President of the Shiromani Gurdwara Prabandhak Committee on 15 August 1947, was replaced by Udham Singh Nagoke on 28 June 1948. Recalling the promises of the Congress particularly its resolution of 1929 and expressing their faith and trust in the Congress leaders, the Akalis resolved in March 1948 that all their legislatures should join the Congress Party. This was done on 18 March 1948.

In June 1948, Giani Kartar Singh joined the Congress Party and became a minister in the Punjab Cabinet.[11] Master Tara Singh, the Akali leader saw in the Sikhs constituting a majority in a strategic province, the possibility of the Akali becoming the exclusive repository of power independently of the Congress. In his presidential address delivered at the Second Sikh Students Federation Conference at Ludhiana on 24-25 April 1948, he stressed the need to preserve the separate political integrity to the Sikhs and insisted that the Shiromani Akali Dal should retain its independent authority to take political decision on behalf of the Panth. The movement for redrawing State boundaries on the basis of linguistic and cultural homogeneity has had a long history Congress Party had accepted the idea of the linguistic redistribution of provinces at its Nagpur Session in 1920. In 1927, Indian National Congress suggested regarding the need of linguistic States.[12]

Mahatma Gandhi urged the Congress government to carry out the pledge to reorganize the provinces according to language after the country gained independence in August 1947. The government appointed Dar Commission to examine the question of linguistic States on 17 June 1948. In July 1948, a new political state named Pepsu was established as a result of the independence. It consisted of Patiala and other Princely States in the East Punjab. Sardar Patel while performing its inaugural ceremony termed it as 'Homeland of the Sikhs' and it was exploited by the Akalis as a justification in favour of its merger into the Sikh majority districts of Punjab and formation of Punjabi language State.[13]

With the exception of Partap Singh Kairon, president, the Sikh members of the East Punjab States Assembly have adopted a 13-point charter of demands from the Constituent Assembly. As India has become physically and emotionally a part of the national sentiment, the Linguistic Provinces Commission suggested that no additional provinces be created for the time being. At its Jaipur session in 1948, the Indian National Congress established a committee to examine the issue of linguistic province and assess the situation in light of the Dar Commission's recommendations. Jawaharlal Nehru, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel, and Dr. Pattabhi Sitaramayya made up the J.V.P. Committee, which was the first Congress committee to issue a warning against the linguistic concept. [14] The Committee made a special reference to the problem of State reorganization of the northern area and categorically expressed itself against any such rectification of the boundaries in the immediate future. The Punjab was excluded from the purview of the Dar Commission followed by the J.V.P. Committee on account of various problems then facing the province as a result of the partition.[15]

"Partition of the country has undoubtedly made many of us hesitant about changing the map of India," Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru observed, relating the shift in the Congress's stance to the division. "That at a time when the world was hanging on the verge of crisis, it was extraordinary unwise to unsettle and uproot the whole of India on the basis of a theoretical approach on linguistic division," the statement continued. "We must give the utmost to developing a sense of unity in India and anything that might come in the way of that unity might perhaps be delayed a little." [16]

According to *the Tribune*, the government recognized Punjabi and Hindi as the official languages of East Punjab. They now have equal standing in offices, courts, and educational institutions. However, compared to its sibling languages, such as Hindi, Bengali, Marathi, Gujrati, and others, Punjabi was significantly less developed than Hindi and worse in many ways. At its meeting on June 9, 1949, the Punjab University Senate rejected by a majority vote the proposal to adopt Punjabi as the medium of instruction, despite the Sikh senators' agreement to allow it to be written in Devnagri scripts in addition to its own Gurmukhi script, which differed from the Hindu sentiment.[17]

The Akali Dal extended its support to Bhim Sen Sachar who became Chief Minister on 6 April 1949. In October 1949, Sachar Formula was evolved by Giani Kartar Singh and the Chief Minister Bhim Sen Sahcar to accommodate the Sikh concern for Punjabi. It was

announced on 2 October 1949. The proposals were signed by the other members Ujjal Singh and Gopi Chand Bhargava. The Punjab Government announced its decision to adopt a language formula, known as Sachar Formula which provided for a notional division of the province into two Zones, a Punjabi Zone and Hindi Zone. The Punjabi Zone of the carving of Sachar Formula consisted of the districts of Amritsar, Jullundur, Gurdaspur, Ferozepur, Ludhiana and Hoshiarpur, all the portions of Hissar district, lying to the east of Ferozepur, Patiala side of the Ghaggar river and Ropar, and Kharar tehsil of Ambala district, to the Hindi Zone were assigned the districts of Gurgaon, Rohtak, Kamal, all portions of Hissar district lying to the south of Ghaggar river and Jagadhari and Naraingarh Tehsils of Ambala district and Kangra. The remaining areas Simla, Ambala, Chandigarh and Sirsa were declared bilingual/38 Bhim Sen Sachar's Ministry lasted for a bare six months, as the Akali group decided to switch its support to Bhargava.

Following his return to office on October 18, 1949, Dr. Gopi Chand Bhargava resigned as Chief Minister on January 20, 1951. Conventions, conferences, rallies, and comments by various figures over the Punjabi Suba issue followed in 1950. In an article published in the daily "Ajit" around this time, Master Tara Singh came to the conclusion that it should be clear that a peaceful India is impossible without a happy and devoted populace. The merger was canceled at a meeting of the Akali Dal's Working Committee on July 30, 1950, on the grounds that the great leaders' constructive sympathy and support had not materialized. Jaswant Singh Duggal was the only Akali member to leave the Congress Party, though. The Akali members who remained in the Congress Party defended their stance by arguing that the Panth would benefit more from their continuing membership in the Congress Party.[18]

Giani Kartar Singh, the Revenue Minister, Punjab, remarked that Akali legislators had served the Panth and that they hoped to serve it better. In a speech at Amritsar, Isher Singh Majhail who was a Cabinet Minister in the Gopi Chand Bhargava's ministry, said that even if the situation was viewed from selfish angle, the Sikhs should continue in the Congress Party for they now enjoyed 50 percent representation in the Cabinet. The Punjab Congress decided to oppose the Akali demand of an autonomous status for Punjabi speaking State. On 15 December 1950, Partap Singh Kairon called an All India Congress Sikh Convention in which all the leading Congress Sikh made attack on Akali Dal's demand of Punjabi Suba. Among those who attended the Convention were Giani Zail Singh, Surjit Singh Majithia, Gurdial Singh Dhillon, Jathedar Udharn Singh Nagoke, Sarmukh Singh Chamak and Jathedar Sohan Singh Jallalusman. While addressing the Convention President Sardul Singh Caveeshar advised the Akali leaders that their slogan of Punjabi Suba was synonymous with the slogan raised by Jinnah while demanding Pakistan.[19]

During the Census of 1951, the Hindus by and large declared Hindi as their mother tongue, thus disowning Punjabi. The Hindu press argued that by declaring Gurmukhi as the only script for Punjab, the government had denied them their right to name Punjabi, as their mother tongue. The Shiromani Akali Dal issued a manifesto stating that they are in favour of formation of provinces on a linguistic and cultural basis throughout India but it holds, it is the question of life and death for the Sikhs for a new Punjab to be created immediately. Giani Kartar Singh continued in the Congress Party but resigned later in 1951 when his group was unable to get a sufficient number of tickets for the forth-coming general elections in 1951-52. He again joined the Akali Dal and became its General Secretary.

In 1952, the country's first general elections under the new constitution provided Akali Dal with a chance to address the public. During his electioneering tour, Jawaharlal Nehru vehemently opposed the formation of Punjabi Suba and referred to it as a national divide. When some Punjabi Suba demand activists interrupted him in Patiala on January 4, 1952, with the chants "Le Ke Rahenge Punjabi Suba," Nehru said, "I will not allow India to be divided again." I won't permit any more issues. I would do all in my power to put an end to any unrest that arises anywhere in India.[20]

Sardar Gian Singh Rarewala was the chief minister of the United Front Ministry that the Akalis were able to establish in Pepsu. On April 22, 1952, an Akali-dominated cabinet took over the Congress ministry in Patiala. In all of India, this was the first non-Congress administration to be constituted. Seat reservations for any group were rejected by the Constituent Assembly. However, the Sikhs were unwilling to accept such a choice, in contrast to other communities. They demanded that no other community be associated with their case. It was Master Tara Singh's recurrent theme that, "the Englishman has gone, but our (Sikhs) liberty has not come. For us the so-called liberty is simply a change of masters black for white. Under the grab of democracy and secularism our Panth, our liberty and our religion are being crushed." [21]

The Shiromani Akali Dal now got extremely keen on demanding the amalgamation of the Punjab-speaking regions of the Pepsu and the Punjab. In December 1952, Potti Sriramula, one of the oldest Congress leader of Andhra queered the pitch by starting a fast unto death. Four days after his death, the Prime Minister announced the government's decision to form a State of Andhra by the partition of Madras and it came into being in October 1953.[22] The problem of reorganisation of the provinces in India became emergent because with the programme of large scale planning, it was essential to have ending political units.

In order to increase the welfare of the citizens of each constitutional unit and the country overall, the Parliament created the States Reorganisation Commission on December 29, 1953, to look into the issue of reorganizing the States of the Indian Union "objectively and dispassionately." The Commission named Kavalam Madhava Pannikar, the Indian ambassador in Egypt at the time, Hariday Nath Kunzru, a member of the Council of States at the time, and Saiyed Fazl Ali, the governor of Orissa, as its chairman. Sikhs applauded the Commission's establishment since it gives them a chance to present their Punjabi Suba case and receive a decision. The Akali Dal further argued that the demand for Punjabi Suba was in line with demands in other parts of India for the linguistic reorganisation of States. It further said that the Punjabi was a distinct language and had been so recognised in the Indian constitution. It is also endowed with a special script known as Gurmukhi which is not derived from Devnagri script of Hindi but from Brahmi. [23]

The areas claimed to be included in the proposed Punjabi speaking State would be the districts of Gurdaspur, Amritsar, Ferozepur, Ludhiana, Jullundur, Hosiarpur, Ambala, Kamal (except Panipat tehsil) and tehsils of Sirsa and Fatehabad and sub-tehsil Tohana of Hissar district, Patiala, Bamala, Bhatinda, Kapurthala, Fatehgarh Sahib and Sangrur (except Jind, Nirwana tehsils) and Ganganagar district in Rajasthan. The economically backward people of Haryana demanded a separate State for they alleged that they had been discriminated by the more advanced Punjabis in all fields of education, administration, politics, trade and commerce. 19 members of Punjab legislature and two members of Parliament representing the Ambala division in a memorandum submitted to the States Reorganisation Commission, urged the formation of new State, comprising the Hindi-speaking areas of Punjab, Pepsu and Himachal Pradesh, Delhi, Meerut and Agra division of U.P.[24]

Prof. Sher Singh, Sri Chand, Sri Ram Sharma, and 50 other Haryana M.L.A.s reaffirmed their call for the Haryana Prant in the Punjab Legislative Assembly. Nearly 90% of Haryana Prant residents, according to Prof. Sher Singh, believe that they should be "linked with an area with the people of which they have everything in common with regard to language, dress, habits, and customs (and) with whom they were united before the great revolt of 1857 to form a separate State." [25]

The Congress Government's memorandum appealed for Greater Punjab, which includes Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Pepsu, and a few U.P. districts. In October 1955, the States Reorganization Commission released its report. Since there was no "minimum measure of agreement necessary for making the change in the present setup" among Punjabi citizens, the Akali Dal's demand for a Punjabi-speaking state was rejected by the States Reorganisation Commission. The combination of Punjab, Papsu, and Himachal Pradesh was suggested by the Commission. The report was well received by the Punjab Pradesh Congress Committee's Executive Committee. The Commission cited two main arguments in favor of the State's continuation: first, that Pepsu should be permitted to remain as a Sikh homeland; and second, that giving in to the demands for either a Maha Punjab or a Punjabi-speaking State would be the alternative. However, because they were meant to tip the scales in favor of one of the two major groups, the government saw both of these demands as having a community nature.[26]

Giani Kartar Singh claimed that 13 of the 14 states designated by the constitution had been reorganized according to language, with the exception of Punjabi Suba, which had not been established due to suspicions about Sikh allegiance. On October 16, 1955, Master Tara Singh called a Sikh representative convention to Amritsar. The States Reorganisation Commission was criticized by the convention for handling Sikh grievances with "undisguised bias" and rejected its recommendations.[27]

Master Tara Singh was asked by Jawaharlal Nehru to discuss the Punjab issue, and on January 22, 1956, a compromise formula known as the Regional Formula was developed. To protect the interests of the language communities, the Punjab State was partitioned linguistically using the Regional Formula. After much discussion, Master Tara Singh and the Akalis approved the regional plan. In a March 15, 1956, press release outlining the rationale behind the plan's approval, Master Tara Singh claimed that while the plan

partially met Sikh aspirations, it also prevented them from gaining the ability to rule over others, which could have made them "undemocratic and narrow-minded." [28]

The State was split into Punjabi-speaking and Hindi-speaking regions under the Regional Formula. Regarding the regional scheme, the Punjab Pradesh Congress was polarized. One faction opposed coercion of any kind and argued that Punjabi should not be forced onto those who choose not to participate in the administration and trade. The plan was opposed by the majority of Haryana's Congress M.L.As. Giani Kartar Singh, the leader of the opposing faction, emphasized that any change to the Regional Formula would encourage oppositional agitation. A delegation of fifty members of the Congress presented a memorandum to the Prime Minister. Fourteen members of the Congress Legislative Party resigned from the Congress, they were: Jagat Narain, Shrimati Sita Devi, Ralla Ram, Suraj Bhan, Vaid Ram Dyal and Sher Singh. It strengthened the communal trends in the organisation, it sharply divided the Hindu and Sikh Congressmen. [29]

The Punjab State Congress's then-president, Partap Singh Kairon, was against the state being divided based on language. Kairon was elected in lieu of Bhim Sen Sachar because Pt. Nehru believed that he was essential to Punjab. On January 23, 1956, Partap Singh Kairon was appointed Punjab's chief minister. By a vote of 350-353, the Akali Dal General Conference in November 1956 agreed to combine the Akali Party with the Congress. On April 3, 1957, Partap Singh Kairon was chosen as the Congress Assembly Party's leader following the 1957 assembly election. He appointed two former Akalis, Gian Singh Rarewala and Giani Kartar Singh, to his Cabinet and established the Congress Ministry. The largest group in the Congress Party at this time was that of Partap Singh Kairon with a following of about 55 members. [30]

In order to propose a solution to the language tangle, the Punjab government established a 20-member language committee in 1960, which was chaired by Mr. Gadgil, the state governor. The Sikhs believed that this Committee was formed to suggest two scripts for Punjabi, thereby destroying the Sachar Formula and Regional Formula, which permitted Punjabi to be written exclusively in Gurmukhi script, since it was also appointed in response to threats from "Save Hindi" agitators. In March 1960, the Shiromani Gurdwara Prabandhak Committee decided to abstain from this 20-member language committee. It stated that dividing Punjab into Punjabi and Hindi is the only way to address the province's linguistic issues. In the March 1960 elections, Master Tara Singh emerged victorious. Kartar Singh, Gian Singh Rarewala, and Partap Singh Kairon ran against the Akali Dal in the election. Shiromani Gurdwara Prabandhak Committee On the eve of the election, the Sikh masses were affected by the Congress High Command's decision on December 23, 1956, to split the State of Bombay into two States, Maharashtra and Gujarat. This strengthened the Sikhs' demand for an own Punjabi-speaking population. [31]

On January 19, 1960, the election results were announced. The Akali Dal achieved a stunning triumph. The Akali Dal soon started informing the Sikh populace that a morcha for Punjabi Suba will be started right away. The Akali Dal's challenge was accepted by the Punjab Congress Government. On May 24, 1960, Master Tara Singh and other Akalis were taken into custody in Amritsar. On May 24, 1960, and August 15, 1960, Pt. Nehru chastised Akalis' demand. Sant Fateh Singh went to great lengths on December 18, 1960, to persuade the Prime Minister to grant the justifiable request for a Punjabi province based solely on linguistic grounds. Jawaharlal Nehru was now willing to give up the Punjabi language's rights. At a speech in Chandigarh on 20 December 1960, Nehru said that Punjabi was the dominant language of the Punjab and it must be promoted in every way. [32]

The Prime Minister personally invited Sant Fateh Singh to meet with him in Delhi on February 8, 1961, in a letter dated January 23, 1961. The plan for the linguistic division of the states was considered by the Akali Dal Working Committee. Nehru met with Sant Fateh Singh several times. The leaders who opposed Punjabi suba's formation worked to make sure parleys didn't succeed. Nehru informed Sant Fateh Singh during their meeting on May 12, 1961, that the creation of the Punjabi suba was neither in the nation's or Punjab's best interests. In the meantime Master Tara Singh felt that there had been a set back to his leadership and Sant Fateh Singh had emerged as his rival. He decided to go on a fast unto death himself from 15 August 1961 for the creation of Punjabi suba. [33]

The Enquiry Commission comprising S.K. Das, Former Chief Justice of India, M.C. Chagla and C.P. Ramaswamy Ayyer were appointed to hear the grievances of the Sikhs of the Punjab. The Commission submitted its report in February 1962. It reported that no discrimination could be established against the Sikhs as they were over represented in the public services and in the Punjab Cabinet. The Prime Minister Nehru remained opposed to the creation of Punjabi Suba until the end of his life. Partap Singh Kairon had dominated Punjab politics from 1956 till 1964, period in which he had the backing of Pt.

Nehru. He opposed to the creation of a Punjabi speaking State on political consideration as he feared that the Congress would go out of office in Punjab and that his political career would suffer a set back if Punjabi speaking State was created.[34]

After the war, the Central Government took initiative to resolve the Punjab problem. A Cabinet Committee consisting of Y.B. Chavan, Indira Gandhi and Mahavir Tyagi and assisted by a 22 member Parliamentary Consultative Committee, headed by Lok Sabha Speaker Hukam Singh was appointed to tackle the long-standing issue of reorganisation of Punjab.[35] At a press conference on 14 July 1965, Master Tara Singh after scathing criticism of the Congress and Sant Fateh Singh, declared that he had decided to re-enter politics to ensure the dignity, honour and freedom of the Panth. He said that the Sikhs should be given right to determine their political status in a State where they should feel their religion and culture to be safe. The Punjab Congress had mix reaction about the Cabinet Committee and Consultative Committee of Parliament. Punjab Pradesh Congress held its meeting on 1 October 1965, it was decided that the demand of Punjabi Suba be opposed.[36]

On several occasions, the Punjab government clearly said that Punjab should remain unified, according to Comrade Ram Kishan, the chief minister of Punjab, Home Minister Darbara Singh, and Transport Minister Gurdial Singh Dhillion. The Consultative Committee received numerous memoranda from the different political parties and organizations whose opinions were widely known at this point. The Congress disagreed on the matter. The Cabinet Committee and Consultative Committee of Parliament elicited conflicting responses from the Punjab Congress. At its meeting on October 1, 1965, the Punjab Pradesh Congress agreed to oppose Punjabi Suba's demand.[37]

Following the tragic death of Lai Bahadur Shastri in Tashkent, Mrs. Indira Gandhi was now the prime minister. The way the Congress saw the Punjab issue was also influenced by the party's internal strife. Mahavir Tyagi, a key Committee member, resigned from the Cabinet due to the resulting circumstances. Despite her opposition to the Punjabi Suba concept, Indira Gandhi was powerless to stop the demand by 1966 because it had become so powerful. On March 9, 1966, the Congress Working Committee, which Kamraj presided over, did, however, adopt a resolution in favor of a Punjabi-speaking state.[38]

Y.B. Chavan observed, "A decision on the demand for a Punjabi State would not be delayed because of the geographical position of the Punjab". Prime Minister Mrs. Indira Gandhi was firm in her decision said, "The Working Committee has passed a resolution and now we (the Government) have to implement. The government of India approved in principle the report of the Parliamentary Committee recommending that Punjab should be reorganized on linguistic basis and setup a Commission known as a Punjab Boundary Commission on 23 April 1966.[39] The Commission was required to apply the linguistic principle with due regard to the Census figures of 1961 and other relevant consideration and may also take into consideration other factors such as (a) administrative convenience (b) economic well-being (c) geo-graphical contiguity d) facility of communication. Master Tara Singh said at Jullundur that "to make the 1961 Census, the basis of division would mean sabotaging the Suba by reducing its size and making it economically weak". The Commission held its meeting from 9 May 1966 till 23 May 1966. The Punjab Reorganisation Act was approved by both the houses. It received the President's assent on 18 September 1966. The new Punjab was reduced to just 20, 254 square miles and 11.58 million population out of when 56 percent were Sikhs. It came into existence on 1 November 1966.[40]

Conclusion

The Akali Dal, advocating for a separate Punjabi-speaking state, used the media to emphasize the cultural, linguistic, and religious rights of the Sikh community. From 1955, when the Akali Dal first formally demanded a Punjabi Suba, their supporters used regional newspapers to highlight the neglect of Punjabi-speaking people under the Congress government. These media outlets framed the movement as a fight for justice and cultural preservation. Conversely, the Congress, which dominated national media, viewed the demand for a separate state as a threat to national unity. Congress-aligned newspapers, particularly from 1959 onward, portrayed the movement as divisive, warning that creating a separate Punjabi Suba could lead to similar demands from other regions, jeopardizing India's territorial integrity. Regional newspapers in Punjab, reflecting the state's growing polarization, reported on protests and public opinion from 1960 to 1966, often showing strong support for the Akali cause. Coverage of the Akali rallies and Congress's counteractions reflected the intense local involvement in the movement. The media's portrayal of the conflict played a crucial role in shaping political alignments and public sentiment. It not only highlighted the regional and ideological divides but also mobilized people on both sides. The press, through its framing of the issue, reinforced the battle between regional autonomy and national unity, a theme that significantly influenced the political future of Punjab and India.

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